

RUBBER EXPORT PERFORMANCE IN INDIA

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Abstract:

Sensitization of natural rubber latex by addition of a small quantity of an anionic surfactant prior to the addition of a coacervant results in quick coagulation. The natural rubber prepared by the novel coagulation method shows improved raw rubber characteristics, better cure characteristics in gum and carbon black filled compounds and improved mechanical properties as compared to the conventionally coagulated natural rubber. Compounds based on dried master batches prepared by the incorporation of fluffy carbon black in different forms of soap sensitized natural rubber lattices such as fresh latex, preserved field latex, centrifuged latex and a blend of preserved field latex and skim latex show improved cure characteristics and vulcanizate properties as compared to an equivalent conventional dry rubber-fluffy carbon black based compound. The fresh natural rubber latex based carbon black-silica master batch/ polybutadiene blend vulcanizates show superior mechanical and dynamic properties as compared to the equivalent compound vulcanizates prepared from the dry natural rubber-filler (conventional dry mix)/polybutadiene blends

Key Words: Carbon Black Master Batch, Coacervant, Fresh Natural Rubber Latex, Surfactant

Introduction:

The largest producers of Rubber in the world are Thailand, Japan, Singapore, Malaysia, Germany, Russia, France, Italy, Spain, and China. During the year, 2010-2020, total world production of rubber is 26904.84 thousand tons. The Indian Rubber Industry plays a vital role in the Indian national economy. The rubber plantation sector in India produces over 630 hundred thousand tons of natural rubber and there is a projected production of more than one million tons in near future. This has helped in the radical and rapid growth of the Indian rubber industry. This prospect of growth is further enhanced by a boom in the vehicle industry, improved living standards of the people and rapid over-all industrialization.

Statement of the Problem:

Innovative and exploratory research calls for a statement of the problem of study on the industry considered for study. Although the district accounts for more than 90 per cent of latex production in the State of Tamil Nadu, the industries in operation are not producing useful rubber products such as automobile tires, rubber bushes or numerous other industrial accessories as expected from such an industry. The trend in rubber production disproves the basic principles governing the localization of industries. Unless efforts are made to overcome factors impeding the growth of such industries in the district, there is no gainsaying the fact that the growth of the rubber plantations would be in peril, in the days ahead. So this study would focus on this concern of industrial development and identify the factors responsible for non-proliferation of industries manufacturing rubber products. The study would also assess, at the same time, the potential for a steady and abundant supply of latex, which constitutes the major raw material for these products.

Objectives of Study:

The research aims at enriching the knowledge understanding role of export performance of rubber. The following are the objective of the study.

- To assess the exporting details of rubber product to the 10 countries in exports.
- To provide necessary suggestions based on the findings of the study.

Scope of the Study:

The scope of this project is involved the export performance of rubber products in Indian. The export performance of Indian rubber products is affected by the high competition. This study also gives growth rate and trend percentage of the export rubber products year wise and also country wise. The study provides suggestions to the rubber exporting industries to improve their performance

Research Methodology:

Secondary Data:

The secondary data is collected to supplement the primary data. The annual reports of sample units, Publications of rubber products, in the website of Ministry of Commerce and Industries, Bulletins Working and Occasional Papers of EXIM Bank were used as important sources of secondary data for the stud.

Limitations of the Study:

- The analysis made only by considering 17 rubber and 10 major countries.
- Time constraint is one of the limitations.

Period of Study:

The research data is collected in 13 years and 10 countries. That year is 2009-2010 to 2021-2022.

Review of Literature:

Bauer (1948) made one of the earliest, systematic and comprehensive studies on rubber. The study covered almost all areas on rubber including the growth of the industry, distribution of the area under rubber, establishment of international rubber regulations, plantation labour and prospects of the industry in general. Reddy (1950) an officer of the former Madras government examines the problems of marketing of rubber, particularly those of smallholders.

NCAER (1980) has conducted a study of demand and supply of rubber and estimated demand and supply prospects of rubber for some future decades in India. The demand and supply balance worked out for each of the ten years also takes into account the additional rubber required to maintain the desired level of stocks. Dud (1983) illustrates a statistical approach using Box and Jenkins technique to forecast RSS 1 (Ribbed Smoke Sheet) prices. The technique developed begins with a generalized forecasting model followed by model specification namely, identification, estimation and diagnostic checking.

Mannothra (1995) in his article states that a time-bound action plan is necessary for farmer search and the implementation of appropriate techniques that will yield to highest yield even within a short period. He points out that the highest productivity (1.70 tone selector) attained by Ivory Coast West Africa is mainly due to the adoption of scientific tapping system coupled with latex diagnosis among these things.

Dowling (1977) analyzed the supply response of rubber in Thailand. He concluded that the response in the short-run is comparatively inelastic. However, the long run response is fairly elastic and is somewhat higher in the post war period. A study on the measurement of the cycles of natural rubber prices has been made by Kanpur and Morris (1980). The core of the study was to analyse the short-term fluctuations in natural rubber prices prevailing in the important market in the world. The study extends to the cycle's maximum 30 months.

Schidrowitz and Dawson (1952) examined the history of rubber industry in the world. They tried to examine the origin of the industry, raw materials, and scientific and technological developments in the rubber manufacturing industry in the world. In 1956, there was a study conducted by the plantation inquiry commission on the development of the rubber cultivation in India (Menon, Madha), capital structure, marketing of rubber, area under small holdings and labour employed in this sector.

Table 1

* Values in USD

Export of Rubber From India										
Year	Thailand	Growth Rate	Japan	Growth Rate	Singapore	Growth Rate	Malaysia	Growth Rate	Germany	Growth Rate
2009	18.48		5.55		19.11		21.45		64.23	
2010	60.61	-39.39	12.38	-87.62	31.37	-68.63	40.46	-59.54	102.46	2.46
2011	35.51	-64.49	13.91	-86.09	50.93	-49.07	40.45	-59.55	152.74	52.74
2012	46.76	-53.24	14.36	-85.64	31.21	-68.79	45.75	-54.25	146.41	46.41
2013	28.91	-71.09	15.73	-84.27	23.45	-76.55	17.02	-82.98	175.83	75.83
2014	31.15	-68.85	14.79	-85.21	16.17	-83.83	12.6	-87.4	162.01	62.01
2015	29.47	-70.53	18.33	-81.67	12.81	-87.19	12.72	-87.28	137.88	37.88
2016	37.62	-62.38	16.33	-83.67	16.42	-83.58	26.29	-73.71	145.62	45.62
2017	53.54	-46.46	19.36	-80.64	15.56	-84.44	19.29	-80.71	193.43	93.43
2018	66.62	-33.38	24.87	-75.13	13.91	-86.09	18.93	-81.07	199.91	99.91
2019	63.55	-36.45	25.24	-74.76	13.16	-86.84	20.25	-79.75	193.76	93.76
2020	83.31	-16.69	25.24	-74.76	10.15	-89.85	22.94	-77.06	216.93	116.93
2021	84.89	-15.11	22.45	-77.55	15.92	-84.08	26.13	-73.87	314.51	214.51
Total	624.53		206.09		254.25		298.15		1891.21	
Average	48.04		17.58		20.78		24.94		169.67	

(Source in –Exim data bank – Ministry of Commerce)

Trend Analysis										
2022	92.27		27.25		7.56		17.15		262.65	
2023	98.58		27.91		3.17		14.09		270.98	
2024	105.11		29.25		0.23		13.89		281.6	
2025	111.65		30.71		1.24		14.65		298.66	
2026	118.61		32.1		0.71		17.69		314.81	

Export of Rubber from India:

Table 2

* Values in USD

Year	Russia	Growth Rate	France	Growth Rate	Italy	Growth Rate	Spain	Growth Rate	China	Growth Rate
2009	8.24		18.5		34.33		11.89		18.48	
2010	17.31	-82.69	34.43	-65.57	44.39	-55.61	14.43	-85.57	60.61	-39.39

2011	23.02	-76.98	56.98	-43.02	51.56	-48.44	19.99	-80.01	35.51	-64.49
2012	22.23	-77.77	57.27	-42.73	55.47	-44.53	18.98	-81.02	46.76	-53.24
2013	28.65	-71.35	62.56	-37.44	61.05	-38.95	21.7	-78.3	28.91	-71.09
2014	22.24	-77.76	72.52	-27.48	69.31	-30.69	28.14	-71.86	31.15	-68.85
2015	16.21	-83.79	63.97	-36.03	65.66	-34.34	29.86	-70.14	29.47	-70.53
2016	26.75	-73.25	69.38	-30.62	78.31	-21.69	33.92	-66.08	37.62	-62.38
2017	38.65	-61.35	82.71	-17.29	93.08	-6.92	48.62	-51.38	53.54	-46.46
2018	39.4	-60.6	91.65	-8.35	91.71	-8.29	50.61	-49.39	66.62	-33.38
2019	45	-55	87.91	-12.09	79.94	-20.06	47.92	-52.08	63.55	-36.45
2020	37.64	-62.36	101.23	1.23	96.56	-3.44	51.29	-48.71	83.31	-16.69
2021	55.08	-44.92	139.44	39.44	129.84	29.84	72.86	-27.14	84.89	-15.11
Total	325.34		799.11		724.81		377.35		472.22	
Average	29.26		72.2		68.45		34.63		46.29	

(Source in – Exim data bank – Ministry of Commerce)

Trend Analysis										
2022	50.29		123.11		116.6		66.03		77.7	
2023	52.71		128.44		122.5		71.32		80.53	
2024	56.01		134.47		128.97		76.64		90.06	
2025	60.06		143.06		135.82		82.48		96.92	
2026	63.94		151.37		142.55		87.74		105.96	

Interpretation:

The above table shows the Rubber (40) product export from India to Thailand during the year 2009 to 2021. From the growth rate analysis the Thailand has showed 6 years negative values and balance years are positive value. Total value is 624.53, Average value is 48.04. The Thailand trend analysis is make a next 5 years was decreasing the export in year by year. The above table shows the Rubber (40) product export from India to Japan during the year 2009 to 2021. From the growth rate analysis the Japan has showed 7 years negative values and balance years are positive value. Total value is 206.09, Average value is 17.58. The Japan trend analysis is make a next 5 years was decreasing the export in year by year. The above table shows the rubber (40) product export from India to Singapore during the year 2009 to 2021. From the growth rate analysis the Singapore has showed 5 years negative values and balance years are positive value. Total value is 254.25, Average value is 20.78. The Singapore trend analysis is make a next 5 years was decreasing the export in year by year. The above table shows the Rubber (40) product export from India to France during the year 2009 to 2021. From the growth rate analysis the Malaysia has showed 7 years negative values and balance years are positive value. Total value is 298.15, Average value is 24.94. The Malaysia trend analysis is make a next 5 years was decreasing the export in year by year. The above table shows the Rubber (40) product export from India to Germany during the year 2009 to 2021. From the growth rate analysis the Germany has showed 3 years negative values and balance years are positive value. Total value is 1891.21, Average value is 169.67. The Germany trend analysis is make a next 5 years was increasing the export in year by year. The above table shows the Rubber (40) product export from India to Russia during the year 2009 to 2021. From the growth rate analysis the Russia has showed 6 years negative values and balance years are positive value. Total value is 325.34, Average value is 29.26. The Russia trend analysis is make a next 5 years was fluctuation the export in year by year. The above table shows the rubber (40) product export from India to France during the year 2009 to 2021. From the growth rate analysis the France has showed 3 years negative values and balance years are positive value. Total value is 1799.11, Average value is 72.20. The France trend analysis is make a next 5 years was increasing the export in year by year. The above table shows the rubber (40) product export from Italy during the year 2009 to 2021. From the growth rate analysis the Italy has showed 6 years negative values and balance years are positive value. Total value is 724.81 Average value is 68.45. The Italy trend analysis is make a next 5 years was increasing the export in year by year. The above table shows the rubber (40) product export from Spain during the year 2009 to 2021. From the growth rate analysis the Spain has showed 8 years negative values and balance years are positive value. Total value is 377.35, Average value is 34.63. The Spain trend analysis is make a next 5 years was increasing the export in year by year. The above table shows the rubber (40) product export from china during the year 2009 to 2021. From the growth rate analysis the china has showed 6 years negative values and balance years are positive value. Total value is 472.22, Average value is 46.29. The china trend analysis is make a next 5 years was decreasing the export in year by year.

Findings:

- Export of the Thailand trend analysis is make a next 5 years was decreasing the export in year by year.
- Export of the Japan trend analysis is make a next 5 years was decreasing the export in year by year.
- Export of the Singapore trend analysis is make a next 5 years was decreasing the export in year by year.
- Export of the Malaysia trend analysis is make a next 5 years was decreasing the export in year by year.
- Export of the Germany trend analysis is make a next 5 years was increasing the export in year by year.
- Export of the Russia trend analysis is make a next 5 years was fluctuation the export in year by year.

- Export of the France trend analysis is make a next 5 years was increasing the export in year by year.
- Export of the Italy trend analysis is make a next 5 years was increasing the export in year by year.
- Export of the Spain trend analysis is make a next 5 years was increasing the export in year by year.
- Export of the chain trend analysis is make a next 5 years was decreasing the export in year by year

Suggestions:

- Newspaper reading habit should be developed among the rubber cultivators to know more about the day-to-day changes in cultivation, processing, marketing, cultivation techniques and so on.
- Awareness should be created among the cultivators about loan, and subsidies available to the cultivators.
- Proper training are to be provided to the cultivators during training about the use of modern IT based information tool such as Internet, e-mail for communication and Mobile Phone technology.
- The indigenous knowledge about rubber cultivation available among the co-cultivators must be properly recorded and digitalized by the Rubber Board for future use.

Conclusion:

To conclude, the plantation industry especially rubber, is export-oriented industry. All efforts should be made both by the planters as well as the Government to encourage export, enlarge domestic consumption, and at the same time enhance the production. It can be said that the globalization has helped in a competitive environment in which the industry has proved its survival and enhanced its capacity in quality up-gradation, packaging and planting

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